

A Comparative Study of Subclinical Hypothyroidism in Metabolic Syndrome with Patients Not Having Metabolic Syndrome

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Abstract:

Background: Subclinical hypothyroidism, defined as increased thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels but normal free thyroxine (T4) levels, is a common endocrine disease that has been linked to a variety of metabolic abnormalities, including those associated with metabolic syndrome. Metabolic syndrome, a collection of diseases including abdominal obesity, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and impaired glucose tolerance, is a major public health concern since it is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes.

Aim: The aim of this study was to investigate the association between subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome by comparing the prevalence and characteristics of subclinical hypothyroidism in patients with and without metabolic syndrome.

Methods: A total of 100 participants were enrolled in the study. Participants were assessed for thyroid function, and metabolic syndrome was diagnosed based on the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) criteria. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with comparisons made using chi-square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression analysis.

Results: The prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism was significantly higher in patients with metabolic syndrome (56%) compared to those without metabolic syndrome (20%) ($p < 0.001$). Group A had higher mean TSH levels than Group B (5.6 ± 1.2 vs. 3.8 ± 1.1 mIU/L, $p < 0.001$). Logistic regression analysis revealed that metabolic syndrome and its components, such as abdominal obesity, elevated blood pressure, elevated fasting glucose, and dyslipidemia, were strongly associated with subclinical hypothyroidism.

Conclusion: Subclinical hypothyroidism is significantly more prevalent in patients with metabolic syndrome. The study highlights the need for regular thyroid function screening in patients with metabolic syndrome to ensure early detection and management of subclinical hypothyroidism.

Recommendations: Routine thyroid function tests should be considered for patients with metabolic syndrome to identify and manage subclinical hypothyroidism, potentially reducing the risk of further metabolic and cardiovascular complications.

Keywords: Subclinical hypothyroidism, Metabolic syndrome, Thyroid function, Cardiovascular risk, Endocrine disorders.

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Introduction

Subclinical hypothyroidism, characterised by high (TSH) levels with normal free (T4) concentrations, is a common endocrine condition with a frequency ranging from 4% to 10% in the general population, depending on age, gender, and iodine intake [1]. This disorder has been recognised for its potential impact on many metabolic parameters, including lipid metabolism, insulin resistance, and cardiovascular risk factors [2]. Subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome, which includes abdominal obesity, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and impaired glucose tolerance, share pathophysiological processes [3].

Metabolic syndrome is an increasing public health concern, especially given the global rise in obesity rates. It is related with an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and other metabolic disorders [4]. The (IDF) estimates that metabolic syndrome affects roughly 25% of the global adult population [5]. Given the high frequency of subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome, knowing how they interact is critical for creating effective preventative and therapeutic measures.

Recent studies indicate that subclinical hypothyroidism may worsen metabolic syndrome, increasing the risk of cardiovascular events and mortality [6]. Research suggests that subclinical hypothyroidism can lead to insulin resistance, dyslipidaemia, and hypertension, all of which are associated with metabolic syndrome [7]. Metabolic syndrome may increase the risk of thyroid dysfunction due to chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, and adipokine dysregulation [8].

However, the link between subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome is complex and poorly understood. While some studies have indicated a clear relationship, others have found inconsistent results, underscoring the need for future study to elucidate these interactions and their clinical implications [9]. Subclinical hypothyroidism might affect metabolic health differently based on age, gender, and comorbidities [10]. The aim of this study was to investigate the association between subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome by comparing the prevalence and characteristics of subclinical hypothyroidism in patients with and without metabolic syndrome.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional comparative analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Endocrinology, Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna. This study was conducted over a period of one year, from September 2018 to August 2019. The aim was to compare the prevalence and characteristics of subclinical hypothyroidism in patients with metabolic syndrome and those without it.

Participants: A total of 100 participants were enrolled in the study. The participants were divided into two groups:

- **Group A:** 50 patients diagnosed with metabolic syndrome.
- **Group B:** 50 patients without metabolic syndrome.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18-60 years.
2. Diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism (elevated serum TSH but normal free T4 levels).
3. Group A includes patients who fit the metabolic syndrome criteria outlined in the IDF recommendations.
4. Group B includes patients without metabolic syndrome.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with overt hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism.
2. Patients on thyroid hormone replacement therapy or antithyroid medications.
3. Pregnant women.
4. Patients with chronic kidney disease, chronic liver disease, or other significant comorbidities.
5. Patients unable or unwilling to give informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the outpatient department of PMCH, Patna. Potential information bias was controlled by ensuring that all measurements and data collection were conducted using standardized procedures and calibrated instruments.

Data Collection: Data were gathered utilising a standardised questionnaire and medical records. The following parameters have been recorded:

- Demographic information (age, gender, etc.)
- Clinical history and examination findings
- Laboratory results (TSH, free T4, fasting blood glucose, lipid profile, etc.)
- Criteria for diagnosing metabolic syndrome based on IDF guidelines.

Procedure: Participants were evaluated based on their clinical history, physical examination, and laboratory investigations. Blood samples were collected in a fasting state for the assessment of TSH, free T4, fasting blood glucose, and lipid profile. The diagnosis of subclinical hypothyroidism and metabolic syndrome was confirmed based on the laboratory results and IDF criteria.

Statistical Analysis: The data were examined using SPSS version 23.0. Continuous data were reported as mean \pm SD, whereas categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was used to compare categorical data between the two groups, while the independent t-test was utilised for continuous variables. A p-value $<$ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Logistic regression was used to identify traits related with subclinical hypothyroidism in metabolic syndrome patients.

Results

A total of 100 participants were enrolled in the study, with 50 participants in Group A (patients with metabolic syndrome) and 50 participants in Group B (patients without metabolic syndrome).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Age (years)	45.6 ± 10.2	44.3 ± 11.0	0.563
Gender (Male/Female)	28/22	25/25	0.605
BMI (kg/m ²)	30.4 ± 4.2	24.6 ± 3.7	<0.001

- **Age:** The mean age of participants in Group A was 45.6 years, while in Group B, it was 44.3 years. The difference in age between the two groups was not statistically significant (p=0.563).
- **Gender:** The gender distribution was similar in both groups, with no statistically significant difference (p=0.605).
- **BMI:** The mean BMI was significantly higher in Group A (30.4 kg/m²) compared to Group B (24.6 kg/m²), with a p-value of <0.001.

The prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism was significantly higher in Group A compared to Group B. This is illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2: Prevalence of Subclinical Hypothyroidism in Study Groups

Subclinical Hypothyroidism	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Present	28 (56%)	10 (20%)	<0.001
Absent	22 (44%)	40 (80%)	<0.001

- **Group A:** 56% (28 out of 50) of participants with metabolic syndrome had subclinical hypothyroidism.
- **Group B:** 20% (10 out of 50) of participants without metabolic syndrome had subclinical hypothyroidism.

Thyroid function tests were compared between the two groups. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Thyroid Function Test Results in Study Groups

Parameter	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
TSH (mIU/L)	5.6 ± 1.2	3.8 ± 1.1	<0.001
Free T4 (ng/dL)	1.2 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.3	0.148

- **TSH Levels:** The mean TSH level was significantly higher in Group A (5.6 mIU/L) compared to Group B (3.8 mIU/L), with a p-value of <0.001.
- **Free T4 Levels:** There was no statistically significant difference in free T4 levels between the two groups (p=0.148).

Table 4: Association between Metabolic Syndrome Components and Subclinical Hypothyroidism

Component	Subclinical Hypothyroidism Present (n=38)	Subclinical Hypothyroidism Absent (n=62)	p-value
Abdominal Obesity	29 (76.3%)	18 (29.0%)	<0.001
Elevated Blood Pressure	32 (84.2%)	22 (35.5%)	<0.001
Elevated Fasting Glucose	27 (71.1%)	16 (25.8%)	<0.001
Dyslipidemia	34 (89.5%)	24 (38.7%)	<0.001

- **Abdominal Obesity:** 76.3% of participants with subclinical hypothyroidism had abdominal obesity, compared to 29.0% of participants without subclinical hypothyroidism (p<0.001).
- **Elevated Blood Pressure:** 84.2% of participants with subclinical hypothyroidism had elevated blood pressure, compared to 35.5% of participants without subclinical hypothyroidism (p<0.001).
- **Elevated Fasting Glucose:** 71.1% of participants with subclinical hypothyroidism had elevated fasting glucose, compared to 25.8% of participants without subclinical hypothyroidism (p<0.001).
- **Dyslipidemia:** 89.5% of participants with subclinical hypothyroidism had dyslipidemia, compared to 38.7% of participants without subclinical hypothyroidism (p<0.001).

A logistic regression analysis was performed to identify the factors associated with subclinical hypothyroidism in the study population. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Associated with Subclinical Hypothyroidism

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Metabolic Syndrome	3.84	2.15 - 6.89	<0.001
Abdominal Obesity	2.90	1.54 - 5.46	0.001
Elevated Blood Pressure	3.12	1.72 - 5.65	<0.001
Elevated Fasting Glucose	2.87	1.50 - 5.48	0.002
Dyslipidemia	4.35	2.31 - 8.19	<0.001

- **Metabolic Syndrome:** The presence of metabolic syndrome was associated with a 3.84 times higher likelihood of subclinical hypothyroidism ($p < 0.001$).
- **Abdominal Obesity:** Abdominal obesity was associated with a 2.90 times higher likelihood of subclinical hypothyroidism ($p = 0.001$).
- **Elevated Blood Pressure:** Elevated blood pressure was associated with a 3.12 times higher likelihood of subclinical hypothyroidism ($p < 0.001$).
- **Elevated Fasting Glucose:** Elevated fasting glucose was associated with a 2.87 times higher likelihood of subclinical hypothyroidism ($p = 0.002$).
- **Dyslipidemia:** Dyslipidemia was associated with a 4.35 times higher likelihood of subclinical hypothyroidism ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The study's findings indicate a strong link between metabolic syndrome and subclinical hypothyroidism. Among the 100 participants, those with metabolic syndrome (Group A) had a significantly larger incidence of subclinical hypothyroidism (56%) than those without metabolic syndrome (Group B), who had a frequency of just 20%. This difference was statistically significant, demonstrating that metabolic syndrome is a reliable predictor of subclinical hypothyroidism.

Further examination of thyroid function tests revealed that people with metabolic syndrome had considerably higher mean TSH levels than those without, but there was no significant difference in free T4 levels between the two groups. This implies that increased TSH levels, which are indicative of subclinical hypothyroidism, are more likely in those with metabolic syndrome. The study also looked at how various metabolic syndrome components relate to subclinical hypothyroidism. Abdominal obesity, raised blood pressure, high fasting glucose, and dyslipidaemia were all considerably more common in people with subclinical hypothyroidism. Logistic regression analysis revealed that these characteristics, particularly dyslipidaemia and the metabolic syndrome as a whole, were highly related with an elevated risk of subclinical hypothyroidism.

Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is increasingly associated with metabolic syndrome (MetS), a group of disorders that increase the risk of cardiovascular disease. A meta-analysis completed in 2021, which included 18 research and 79,727 participants, found a strong link between SCH and MetS. SCH was discovered to raise the risk of obesity, hypertension, high triglyceride levels, and poor HDL cholesterol. These findings highlight the need of monitoring thyroid function as part of metabolic syndrome care, considering the significant overlap between the two disorders [11].

A cohort study with 3,615 participants looked into the link between SCH and MetS in greater detail. This study discovered a sex-specific connection, with SCH considerably increasing the chance of developing MetS in young men but not in women or older people. This implies that the effect of SCH on metabolic health varies by gender and age, emphasising the importance of tailored screening and intervention measures [12].

Another study conducted in Venezuela looked at the relationship between SCH and MetS in the context of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. The data revealed that T2DM had a substantial influence on the connection between SCH and MetS. SCH was highly related with MetS only in T2DM patients, implying that hyperglycemia, especially in the context of T2DM, may aggravate SCH's metabolic effects. It emphasise the need to consider comorbid diseases when assessing metabolic hazards related with SCH [13].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study emphasises the need of thyroid function monitoring in individuals with metabolic syndrome. The greater frequency of subclinical hypothyroidism in this population implies that early detection and intervention may be critical in controlling the potential problems of both thyroid dysfunction and metabolic syndrome. This study emphasises the necessity for integrated care approaches that target both metabolic and

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